

LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF USING SYNTACTIC TRANSFORMATIONS IN TRANSLATION

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Abstract: This article deals with the translation process of syntactic transformations and the importance of activating them. The work "Ulysses" by James Joyce was taken to put into practice comparatively with Uzbek translation.

Key words: medium languages, original content, syntactic transformation.

Paying great attention to our native language, especially literature, the president of our country Sh. Mirziyoev expressed his thoughts at the international scientific-practical conference on the topic "Actual issues of studying and promoting Uzbek classical and modern literature at the international level" organized in Tashkent in 2018: "we in Uzbekistan "Literary friendship following the deeply meaningful principle of "eternal friendship", we are paying very serious attention to the issue of translating and publishing masterpieces of world literature into Uzbek," he said.[7] In particular, he expressed his opinion about translation: "until now, most of the works translated from world literature into our mother tongue were done through medium languages, and this situation continues today. Although our young translators know the original language well, in many cases they lack artistic skills. A similar situation can be observed in the field of translation of examples of Uzbek literature into other languages"[7]. It is also worth noting that currently it is urgent to improve the creative skills and competence of young translators in translating the best examples of world literature through the original.[7]

As the Russian translation scientist Novikova Marina mentioned, learning foreign languages has become one of the most important tasks now. Students make some mistakes during translation. Of course, since the main task of higher education institutions is to train qualified specialists, this problem cannot be ignored.

In order for us to observe the mistakes students make in the process of translation, they were given the following sentences from the novel "Ulysses" by the famous English writer James Joyce for the experience, and as a result, samples of word-for-word, free translation were obtained:

1. Two men stood at the verge of the cliff, watching; businessman, boatman [8.p.37].
2. Buck Malligan made way for him to scramble past and, glancing at Haines and Stephan, crossed himself piously with his thumbnail at brow and lips and breastbone [8.p.38].

3.-Seymour's back in town, the young man said, grasping again his spur of rock. Chuked medicine and going in for the army [8.p.38].

4. - Ah, go to God! Buck Mulligan said [8.p.38].

We can see that the students tried to convey the meaning of the original when they translated from the original. According to the analysis of the translation, typical errors were revealed and the reasons were also indicated.

While translating the first sentence, the students did not have any difficulty using the free translation type.

1.Иккиси қоя ёқасида туриб томоша қилишди:тадбиркор,қайиқчи.

-Икки киши қоя ёқасида туриб томоша қилишди:тадбиркор ва қайиқчи.

-Икки киши:тадбиркор ва қайиқчи қоя четида кузатиб турарди.

-Икки киши:тадбиркор ва қайиқчи жар ёқасида кузатиб турарди.

-Икки киши:тадбиркор ва қайиқчи қоя четида атрофга қараб турарди.

It can be concluded that this translation does not pose any specific difficulties.

2.Бак Маллиган қўлини унга сапчиб, Хейнс ва Стефанга назар ташлаб ,бош бармоғини пешонага қўйиб тақводорларча чўқинди.

-Бак Маллиган уни қўлидан сапчиб тутди ва Хейнс ва Стефанга бир қараб қўйди, тақводорларча ўзининг бош бармоғи билан пешона ва кўкрагига чўқиниб олди.

-Бак Маллиган ўтган ишлари учун тавба қилишга ўтди ва Хейнс ва Стефанларга қараб бош бармоғи билан пешона ва кўкрагига уриб чўқинди.

-Бак Маллиган ўтмишини эслади, Хейнс ва Стефанга қараб тақводорлик билан бош бармоғини кўшди, пешона ва кўксига теккизиб сиғинди.

An attempt has been made to convey the original content here.

3.Сеймур шаҳарга қайтди,-деди йигит ва яна қўлидаги тошни ушлади.

-Сеймур шаҳарга қайтди,-деди йигит кейин қўлига яна тошни олди.(қисқартирилган таржима)

-Сеймур шаҳарга қайтди,-деди йигит сўнгра қўлидаги тошини олди.

-Сеймур шаҳарга қайтиб ўз соғлигига эътибор берди ва тиббиёт ёрдамида яна армияга қайтди.

In this translation, it is given out of context.

4. Оҳ, худоим, -деди Бак Маллиган.

-Оллоҳга омонат,-деди Бак Маллиган.

-Оҳ,тавба қилдим,-деди Маллиган.

-Оллоҳга тавба қил,-деди Маллиган.

You can observe the same situation in this sentence. In the translation, the students did not even imagine that the word "God" was omitted. In fact, in reality, be ready to face God; appeal to god; comes in the meaning of the heart being with God.

However, the translator, with a creative approach, brought the translation to the target language in this way.

It can be seen that, from a practical point of view, students can achieve some original content if they use the method of syntactic transformation in the process of translation.

Now, in this table, we present the translation options of the work in which syntactic transformation methods are activated:

Original content	Russian	Uzbek
1. Two men stood at the verge of the cliff, watching: businessman, boatman [7, p.37].	Двое, наблюдая, стояли на краю обрыва- делец и лодочник. [2, стр.26].	Икки киши жар ёқасида туришарди:тадбиркор ва кайиқчи. [1,45-бет]
2. Buck Malligan made way for him to screamble past and, glansing at Haines and Stephan, crossed himself piously with his thumbnail at brow and lips and breastbone [7, p.38].	Бык Маллиган посторонился, пропуская его, и, бросив взгляд на Хейнса и Стивена, ногтем большого пальца набожно перекрестил себе лоб, уста и грудную клетку. [2,стр. 27].	Бак Маллиган уни ёнидан ўтказиб юбориш учун йўл бераркан Хейнс билан Стивенга қараб кўйди-да, бош бармоғининг тирноғи билан манглайи ва кўксини чўқинтирди. [1,46-бет]
3.-Seymour’s back in town, the young man said, grasping again his spur of rock.Chuked medicine and going in for the army [7, p.38].	-А Сеймур опять в городе,-сказал юноша, ухватившись снова за выступ. - Медицину побоку, решил в армию. [2, стр. 27].	--Сеймур шаҳарга қайтиб келди,-деди ёш йигит яна тошнинг четига ёпишиб.- Табобатга тупурди, энди ҳарбий хизматга кирмоқчи. [1,46-бет]
4. - Ah, go to God! Buck Mulligan said [7, p.38].	-Да иди ты,- хмыкнул Бык Маллиган. [2, стр.27].	-Топган гапингни қара,- деди Маллиган. [1,46-бет]

In conclusion, it should be said that it is important for students to widely use the method of syntactic transformation in the sentence and to be able to apply it in the process of translation. However, in the above-mentioned translation options, students tried to reduce the content of the sentences taken from the context.

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